

Tri-Band Millimeter Wave Micro Strip Patch Antenna Array with Finite Ground Structure for 5G Mobile Communication Applications

¹Kirtan Prasad, ²Dr. Bharti Chourasia

¹ME. Scholar, ²Associate Professor & HOD

^{1&2}Department of Electronics & Communication,

^{1&2}RKDF Institute of Science & Technology, SRK University, Bhopal, India

Abstract: The Microstrip patch antenna array design is promising structure for advance communication applications. Array pattern is very hot research area among antenna researchers. Various combination of antenna array designs using in mobile phones and electronics applications. Upper range of Ka band which is more than 18GHz is known as mm wave. This paper proposed tri-band millimeter wave microstrip patch antenna array with finite ground structure. These types of antennas can be used in 5G mobile communication applications. CST microwave studio software is used for design and simulation. Structure of proposed antenna is simple and compact in size of approx $12 \times 35 \times 1.6 \text{ mm}^3$. The simulated results shows that the frequency bandwidth covers 20-28 GHz, at centre frequencies 21.8 GHz, 24.26 GHz and 26.53 GHz respectively for VSWR less than 2. The return loss values are -32.85 dB, -22.64 dB and -18.12 dB for 21.8 GHz, 24.26 GHz and 26.53 GHz resonant frequency. The achieved bandwidth is 435.62, 608.9 and 507.82 MHz respectively.

Keywords: MM-wave, Microstrip, Antenna, Aarray, Bandwidth, Return loss, VSWR.

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite modern research endeavors to send the most effective remote innovations conceivable, the remote business in every case in the long run faces overpowering limit requests for its as of now sent remote advances, welcomed on by the proceeded with advances and disclosures in figuring and interchanges, and the development of new client handsets and use cases, (for example, the need to get to the web). This pattern will happen in the coming a very long time for 4G LTE, suggesting that sooner or later around 2020, remote systems will confront clog, just as the need to execute new advances and designs to appropriately serve the proceeding with requests of bearers and clients. The existence pattern of each new age of cell innovation is commonly 10 years or less (as indicated prior), because of the normal development of PC and correspondences innovation. Our work examines a remote future where versatile information rates extend to the multi gigabit-per-second range, made conceivable by the utilization of steerable antennas and mm-wave range that could all the while bolster portable correspondences and backhaul, with the conceivable union of cell and Wi-Fi services.

Ongoing investigations propose that mm-wave frequencies could be utilized to enlarge the as of now soaked 700 MHz to 2.6 GHz radio range groups for remote correspondences [2]. The reasonability of mm-wave remote interchanges [5], further, mm-wave transporter frequencies take into account bigger bandwidth allotments, which make an interpretation of straightforwardly to higher information move rates. Mm-wave range would permit service suppliers to essentially grow the channel bandwidths a long ways past the current 20 MHz channels utilized by 4G clients [1]. By expanding the RF channel bandwidth for portable radio channels, the information limit is incredibly expanded, while the inactivity for computerized traffic is extraordinarily diminished, in this manner supporting much better web based access and applications that require negligible inertness. Mm-wave frequencies, because of the a lot littler frequency, may abuse polarization and new spatial handling strategies, for example, gigantic MIMO and versatile beamforming [5]. Given this huge bounce in bandwidth and new abilities offered

by mm-waves, the base station-to-gadget joins, just as backhaul interfaces between base stations, will have the option to deal with a lot more prominent limit than the present 4G arranges in profoundly populated regions. Likewise, as administrators keep on diminishing cell inclusion regions to abuse spatial reuse, and execute new agreeable designs, for example, helpful MIMO, transfers, and obstruction alleviation between base stations, the expense per base station will drop as they become increasingly abundant and all the more thickly conveyed in urban regions, making remote backhaul basic for adaptability, brisk arrangement, and decreased continuous working expenses. At long last, rather than the incoherent range utilized by numerous cell administrators today, where the inclusion separations of cell destinations shift broadly more than three octaves of recurrence between 700 MHz and 2.6 GHz, the mm-wave range will have ghastly portions that are generally a lot nearer together, making the spread attributes of various mm-wave groups substantially more practically identical and "homogenous". The 28 GHz and 38 GHz groups are at present accessible with range designations of more than 1 GHz of bandwidth. Initially planned for Local Multipoint Distribution Service (LMDS) use in the late 1990's, these licensees could be utilized for portable cell just as backhaul [5].

2. BACKGROUND

C. K. Ali et al.,[2019] At this moment, is accessible a place of wellbeing plan for twofold band microstrip fix antenna exhibit that works at millimeter wave band with resonance frequencies of 28 GHz, 24.9 GHz and bandwidths of 0.9 GHz, 0.3 GHz independently. The structure was repeated by CST programming, where the zenith increment of 8.42 dBi is cultivated using a little cluster antenna size of estimations "9mm* 8mm* 0.64mm" [Length*Width* Height]; this model can be a promising contender for future 5G mobile phones. Two course of action of substrates materials have been investigated and RO3210 has been picked as a result of its incredible execution with this design.[1]

M. Stanley et al.,[2019] Quick enhancements in remote correspondences request an antenna that can work at twofold repeat groups in a littler size. At the present time, twofold band twofold polarized antenna is proposed for future 5G remote trades that can work at 28 GHz and 39 GHz 5G repeat groups. The proposed antenna is a stacked capacitive coupled fix antenna with curve parasitic parts having twofold polarization capacity. The structure gauges and the antenna execution are discussed in detail. The antenna covers 25.75-30.25 GHz and 36.5-41.5 GHz and has a wide bandwidth in both the repeat groups. The proposed antenna segment has a zenith expansion of 7.14 dBi in the lower band and 6.44 dBi in the higher band. The antenna segment has a littler size of 3.8 mm × 3.8 mm × 1 mm making it fitting for execution of antenna exhibits in compact devices.[2]

R. Tiwari, et al.,[2019] Consistent improvement of plan of microstrip patch antenna for various wellsprings of data and various yield system researcher have been urged to pass on wideband antenna to overhaul the features of MIMO and exhibit design. MIMO advancement has pulled in thought in remote correspondences, since it present gigantic augmentations in data throughput and association reach out without requiring extra transmission limit or transmit control, higher spooky viability and lessened obscuring, a few systems can be associated with improve the microstrip antenna move speed. Cluster design give more yield in UWb go so it will be relevant for LTE remote correspondence and 5G arrange. These consolidate introducing parasitic part either in coplanar or stack configuration, extending the substrate thickness and adjusting the condition of a patch by embeddings openings and examine new possible results of new wideband microstrip patch antenna for individuals to come.[3]

R. Babulkar et al.,[2019] In wireless communication, more than one signals are transmitted in the channel by using the concept of Orthogonal frequency division

multiplexing (OFDM) which efficiently handles the inter symbol interference and utilizes the frequency and available bandwidth efficiently. Whereas for OFDM transmission technique is integrated with MIMO channel which contains multiple transmitter and receiver antenna at both ends.[4]

Z. Gan, et al.,[2018] A wideband circularly polarized (CP) 4×4 millimeterwave antenna cluster made out of novel microstrip antenna segments is shown for IEEE 802.11 aj (45 GHz) application. Through introducing the L-formed branches and abbreviated corners to the microstrip antenna part, an impedance bandwidth of 24.9% and a 3 dB pivotal proportion (AR) bandwidth of 17.3% are practiced. To clarify the effects of the L-formed branches and abbreviated corners, the stage differentiation and adequacy proportions of the 180° and 90° electric field sections at the motivation behind (0,0,r) are isolated and examined. An essential and littler microstrip supporting framework is expected to invigorate the CP antenna cluster, and two-layer PCB sheets are used to execute the proposed exhibit. The electromagnetic imperativeness is coupled to the radiators from the reinforcing framework through the opening cut on the inside ground. The conscious 3 dB AR bandwidth of the antenna cluster is 16% from 41.9 to 49.1 GHz, and the purposeful expansion is all more imperative than 17 dBic inside the band from 41 to 49 GHz.[5]

3. PROPOSED DESIGN

The proposed research work is summarized is as follows-

- To design mm wave microstrip patch antenna array for 5G smart phone communication networks.
- To enhance bandwidth and number of band between 18GHz-28GHz frequency range.
- To calculate other parameters and compare with existing design results.

Figure 1: Flow Chart

Figure 2: Dimension of proposed antenna

Figure 2 is showing dimension of different component of proposed antenna. This dimension is calculated based on standard formulas and optimization. Therefore the dimension of antenna is (LxWxH) 12x35x1.67 mm³. The proposed antenna is based on array pattern so the dimension of single component is 3.99x3.12 mm². The length of feed patch is 7.48mm and width is 0.3mm. The substrate material which is using in proposed antenna is rogers lossy material.

Figure 3: Bottom view of proposed antenna

Figure 2 is showing bottom view of antenna, this is also known as ground structure. There are two types of ground structure, finite and defected ground structure. Proposed antenna is using finite ground structure.

4. SIMULATION RESULT

Scattering parameters is the electrical conduct of straight electrical systems while experiencing different consistent state boosts by electrical signals. S11 speaks to how much power is reflected from the antenna, and subsequently is known as the reflection coefficient or return loss. On the off chance that S11=0 dB, at that point all the force is reflected from the antenna and nothing is transmitted.

Return loss is the distinction, in dB, among forward and reflected force estimated at some random point in a RF framework and, as SWR, doesn't differ with the force level at which it is estimated. Figure 4, 5 and 6, shows the Return Loss (S11) parameters for the proposed antenna, which speaks to the multiband groups of recurrence for which the antenna structured is streamlined for example frequencies running from 20 GHz to 28 GHz with S11 esteem past - 10 dB and the scope of frequencies according to the

outcomes shows that it has a decent bandwidth when contrasted with other microstrip antenna.

Figure 4: Return loss of band-I

The obtained value of S₁₁ or return loss is -32.85 dB for 21.8 GHz resonant frequency, where antenna efficiency is higher.

Figure 5: Return loss of band-II

The obtained value of S₁₁ or return loss is -22.64 dB for 24.26 GHz resonant frequency, where antenna efficiency is higher.

Figure 6: Return loss of band-II

The obtained value of S₁₁ or return loss is -18.12 dB for 26.53 GHz resonant frequency, where antenna efficiency is higher.

Bandwidth, for a framework, could be the scope of frequencies over which the framework delivers a predefined level of execution. A not so much exacting but rather more for all intents and purposes valuable definition will allude to the frequencies past which Execution is corrupted. The bandwidth of an antenna is characterized as "the scope of frequencies inside which the presentation of the antenna, as for some trademark, fits in with a predetermined norm." For broadband antennas, the bandwidth is generally communicated as the proportion of the upper-to-bring down frequencies of adequate activity.

Figure 7: Bandwidth calculation of band-I

For broadband antennas, the bandwidth is expressed as a percentage of the frequency difference (upper minus lower) over the center frequency of the bandwidth. The bandwidth of proposed antenna is 435.62 MHz, (22.026GHz – 21.591GHz), for first band.

Figure 8: Bandwidth calculation of band-II

The bandwidth of antenna is 608.9 MHz, (24.575 GHz – 23.966 GHz), for second band.

Figure 9: Bandwidth calculation of band-III

The bandwidth of antenna is 507.82 MHz, (26.792 GHz – 26.284 GHz), for third band.

Figure 10: 3D Radiation pattern of proposed antenna

The radiation pattern of microstrip or patch antenna is wide. It has low radiation force and restricted recurrence bandwidth. To have a more prominent directivity, an exhibit is framed by utilizing these patch antennas. In the field of antenna plan the term radiation pattern (or antenna pattern or far-field pattern) alludes to the directional (rakish) reliance

of the quality of the radio waves from the antenna or other source. Minor flaps as a rule speak to radiation in undesired ways, so in directional antennas a structure objective is as a rule to lessen the minor projections. Side projections are typically the biggest of the minor flaps. The degree of minor flaps is normally communicated as a proportion of the force thickness in the projection being referred to that of the significant projection.

Table 1: Result summary of proposed antenna

Sr. No.	Parameter	Band-I	Band-II	Band-III
1	S11 or Return Loss	-32.85 dB	-22.64 dB	-18.12 dB
2	Band Width	435.62 MHz	608.9 MHz	507.82 MHz
3	VSWR	1.046	1.159	1.283
4	Resonant Frequency	21.8 GHz	24.26 GHz	26.53 GHz
5	Gain	8.970dB	12.41dB	10.84dB
6	Radiated power	- 0.443 W	- 0.434 W	-0.423W

Table 2: Comparison of proposed design results with previous design results

Sr No.	Parameter	Previous work	Proposed work
1	S11 or Return loss	-22 and -35	-32.85 dB, -22.64 dB and -18.12 dB
2	Band Width	300 and 900 MHz (1200MHz)	435.62, 608.9 and 507.82 MHz (1552.34Mhz)
3	VSWR	1.21 and 1.03	1.046, 1.159 and 1.283
4	Resonant Frequency	24.9 and 28 GHz	21.8, 24.26 and 26.53 GHz
5	Number of band	2	3
6	Gain	5.375 and 8.42 dBi	12.41dBi
7	Design type	Array	Array

Table 2 showing comparison of proposed antenna results with previous design result in terms of bandwidth, return loss, resonant frequency and VSWR etc.

5. CONCLUSION

Therefore above result shows, designed proposed antenna with finite ground gives significant improved result rather than then the existing antenna design in terms of gain and number of band. Return loss is good as it should be more than -10dB. Overall bandwidth is 1200 MHz of previous while 1552.34 MHz of proposed. A tri band, rectangular microstrip patch antenna array is designed and simulated using CST simulation software. The simulation results are presented and discussed. The compact size of designed antenna makes it easy to be incorporated in small devices. Results show that the frequency bandwidth covers 20-28 GHz, at centre frequencies 21.8 GHz, 24.26 GHz and 26.53 GHz respectively for VSWR less than 2, and S11 less than -10 dB. Thus, proposed antenna is a good applicant for 5G smart phone communication applications. The final results satisfy all the parameters of an efficient antenna. The designed antenna works efficiently under all conditions with low return loss and proper impedance matching.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. K. Ali and M. H. Arif, "Dual-band Millimeter-Wave Microstrip Patch Array Antenna for 5G Smartphones," *2019 International journal on Advanced Science and Engineering (ICOASE), Zakho - Duhok, Iraq, 2019*, pp. 181-185.
- [2] M. Stanley et al., "A Dual-Band Dual-Polarised Stacked Patch Antenna for 28 GHz and 39 GHz 5G Millimetre-Wave Communication," *2019 13th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP), Krakow, Poland, 2019*, pp. 1-4.
- [3] R. Tiwari, R. Sharma, R. Dubey "Review of Microstrip Patch Antenna Array and MIMO Antenna for Wireless Applications", *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, ISSN:2349-5162, Vol.6, Issue 5, page no.378-382, May-2019
- [4] R. Babulkar, "A Comprehensive Review on Channel Estimation Techniques in MIMO-OFDM", *SMART MOVES JOURNAL IJOSCIENCE*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 14-18, May 2019. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.24113/ijoscience.v5i5.204>.
- [5] Z. Gan, Z. Tu, Z. Xie, Q. Chu and Y. Yao, "Compact Wideband Circularly Polarized Microstrip Antenna Array for 45 GHz Application," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 66, no. 11, pp. 6388-6392, Nov. 2018.
- [6] H. Khalili, K. Mohammadpour-Aghdam, S. Alamdar and M. Mohammad-Taheri, "Low-Cost Series-Fed Microstrip Antenna Arrays With Extremely Low Sidelobe Levels," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 66, no. 9, pp. 4606-4612, Sept. 2018.
- [7] J. Zhao et al., "A Low-Mutual Coupling Dual-Band Dual-Reflectarray Antenna With the Potentiality of Arbitrary Polarizations," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 16, pp. 3224-3227, 2017.
- [8] C. Kuo, C. Lin and J. Sun, "Modified Microstrip Franklin Array Antenna for Automotive Short-Range Radar Application in Blind Spot Information System," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 16, pp. 1731-1734, 2017.
- [9] B. Cao, H. Wang and Y. Huang, "W-Band High-Gain TE₂₂₀-Mode Slot Antenna Array With Gap Waveguide Feeding Network," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 15, pp. 988-991, 2016.
- [10] D. Shin, S. Park, J. Ahn, K. Han and S. Park, "Design of shorted parasitic rhombic array antenna for 24 GHz rear and side detection system," in *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 9, no. 14, pp. 1581-1586, 19 11 2015.

- [11] M. Poggiani et al., "24-GHz Patch antenna array on cellulose-based materials for green wireless internet applications," in *IET Science, Measurement & Technology*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 342-349, 11 2014.
- [12] T. Mikulasek, A. Georgiadis, A. Collado and J. Lacik, "2 $\times$ 2 Microstrip Patch Antenna Array Fed by Substrate Integrated Waveguide for Radar Applications," in *IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagation Letters*, vol. 12, pp. 1287-1290, 2013.
- [13] L. Han and K. Wu, "24-GHz Bandwidth-Enhanced Microstrip Array Printed on a Single-Layer Electrically-Thin Substrate for Automotive Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 60, no. 5, pp. 2555-2558, May 2012.
- [14] D. T. Pham, H. Subbaraman, M. Y. Chen, X. Xu and R. T. Chen, "Light Weight and Conformal 2-Bit, Phased-Array Antenna With CNT-TFT-Based Phase Shifter on a Flexible Substrate," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 59, no. 12, pp. 4553-4558, Dec. 2011.
- [15] H. Chou, K. Hung and H. Chou, "Design of Periodic Antenna Arrays With the Excitation Phases Synthesized for Optimum Near-Field Patterns via Steepest Descent Method," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 59, no. 11, pp. 4342-4345, Nov. 2011.
- [16] W. Lee, J. Kim and Y. J. Yoon, "Compact Two-Layer Rotman Lens-Fed Microstrip Antenna Array at 24 GHz," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 460-466, Feb. 2011.
- [17] R. Bayderkhani and H. R. Hassani, "Wideband and Low Sidelobe Slot Antenna Fed by Series-Fed Printed Array," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 58, no. 12, pp. 3898-3904, Dec. 2010.
- [18] C. G. Kakoyiannis and P. Constantinou, "Radiation properties and ground-dependent response of compact printed sinusoidal antennas and arrays," in *IET Microwaves, Antennas & Propagation*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 629-642, May 2010.
- [19] R. A. Alhalabi and G. M. Rebeiz, "High-Efficiency Angled-Dipole Antennas for Millimeter-Wave Phased Array Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 3136-3142, Oct. 2008.